

(SHORT COMMUNICATION)

Why is it difficult to enrol patients in clinical cancer research?

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Publication history: Received on 01 May 2020; revised on 20 May 2020; accepted on 21 May 2020

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2020.6.2.0136>

Abstract

Patient recruitments are a crucial part of clinical research, especially in the medical oncology field. Despite its significance, 2-3% of patients with cancer participate in clinical trials. Beyond the bureaucratic and financial barriers in most trials, the recruitment can be directly impacted by the study design, referrals and patient beliefs. Therefore, this study points out the difficulties related to the process of patient recruitments in oncology, followed by options that contribute to their improvement.

Keywords: Medical oncology; Clinical trials; Patient recruitments; Referrals; Research; Cancer patients.

1. Introduction

Advances in oncology directly depend on clinical research. In the past decade, the focus has been on the drug efficacy along with a better toxicity profile. [1] At present, clinical trial designs have become considerably more complex, allowing more personalized treatment. This could potentially avoid unnecessary exposure to patients who are less likely to respond to a specific therapy. [2]

Despite its significance, less than 3% of patients with cancer participate in clinical trials. [3] Beyond the bureaucratic and financial barriers in most trials, the recruitment can be directly impacted by some factors as the study design, referrals and patients' beliefs. [4,5,6] The relevant factors that make it difficult for patient enrolment and some options to improve them are summarized in Table 1.

In order to avoid bias, study designs focus on diminishing the interference of confounder factors by methodically considering inclusion and exclusion criteria. On the one hand, this method often allows a clear interpretation of the study results without considering bias, which is virtually not possible. On the other hand, the real-world scenario is not a controlled environment. This impairs the generalization of clinical trials and the outcomes are frequently worse when compared with those of clinical practice. Additionally, a considerable number of trials do not reach the recruitment target and they are finalized prematurely. On occasion, this happens without the capability to test the objectives proposed previously in the study.

Strategically, clinical research should be seen as a complementary activity to clinical practice. This could diminish the workload of the teams in clinics as the research team is taking over patient care. As a result of this, it is possible to offer

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patients other treatment options. The technology of pre-clinical models and contemporaneous study designs allows for a more reliable drug benefit and toxicity prediction, which is the actual aim of what researchers do and patients seek.

Table 1 Factors related to poor recruitment in cancer clinical trials.

Related Factor	How to improve
Study-related	
Restricted inclusion (lines of treatment) and exclusion criteria (adverse events)	Consider broader inclusion criteria More comprehensive exclusion criteria
Some comorbidities are excluded	Control comorbidities on study arms
Referrals-related	
High workload impair discussion about research	Schedule time to discuss research
Major focus on standard therapy	Protocol presentation to referral teams
Increased work to refer patients	Easier referral procedure (e-mail)
Studies are scarce in most cancer populations	Improve discussion during scientific events
Fewer research units depending on the geographic area	Less bureaucracy, allowing the creation of new research units in less central geographic regions.
Patient-related	
Lack of trust and fear about what is done in clinical research	Improve patient knowledge about the clinical trial through education according to their level of understanding
Hesitation when using experimental drugs	Offer more information about the study drug; provide an evaluation by monitoring possible toxicity effects
Wasting time by receiving a placebo	Avoid placebo whenever possible and explain about the placebo effect
High financial costs due to frequent visits to the study centre	Limit to necessary visits and procedures; offer financial support

2. Conclusion

Therefore, knowing these barriers is the first step to overcome them. Those recommendations should be performed by individualizing the needs of every institution with a focus on patient preferences.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We gratefully acknowledge the support of the collaborative institutions involved in encouraging the elaboration of this article.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All of the authors declare they have no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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How to cite this article

Ramos AP, Bandeira LLB, Ramos AMP, Ferreira RM, Pinheiro BLM, Ramos AMP, da Silva RBS, and de Paula BHR. (2020). Why is it difficult to enrol patients in clinical cancer research? *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 6(2), 163-165.
